

A NEW APPROACH TO PSYCHOLOGICAL ISSUES IN LITERATURE BEING INTRODUCED IN THEIR CLASSES

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ANNOTATION

This article is devoted to the issues of **a new approach to psychological issues in the science of Uzbek literature** .

The theoretical issues of the topic are covered in the article . It reflects the specific characteristics of psychological issues, as well as theoretical and scientific views on the subject .

In the article , it is justified that a new approach to psychological issues in the science of literature is highly effective for the student in studying the work of art. It was determined that it is possible to develop students' knowledge and creativity through it .

Key words: *students' knowledge, students' creativity, theoretical issues, dialectics, literature classes;*

Artistic in literature spirit analytical of artistry main from indicators one to the work soul ato is enough Spirit analytical of the author style , in the image to himself characteristic and artistic skill determines _ of literature his perfection _ greatness , most first of all , the spirit as an analysis of an artistic -aesthetic phenomenon kay level discover done with , human soul , human the heart of dialectics kay level opened with is determined .

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has chosen its own independent socio-economic development path, the fundamental reform of the education system, raising it to the level of modern requirements, and educating a competent generation for the future has become a priority direction of the state policy.

of the article the main goal is the analysis of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes in higher education institutions.

Article 's tasks are as follows:

- researching the problems of using the analysis of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes;
- studying the importance and possibilities of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes;
- creation of methodological support from the analysis of a new approach to psychological issues in Uzbek literature classes (syllabus, technological map, practical training materials);

In the organization of literature classes, several principles of education lead to the formation of a student as a good and spiritual person . For example, *the relevance of teaching to life* . In traditional education, it is the teacher's duty to ensure that lessons are relevant to life. In the lessons aimed at the spiritual maturity of the student, they themselves learn the concepts and laws of science based on life events, and return from theory to life. The teacher

guides this process with guiding questions and tasks. Students respect the scientific and life truths they discover. Theoretical concepts are clarified and deepened by understanding existing existence. By analyzing the personalities of literary characters and the events represented in the work, students learn to find the basis of various events that they may encounter in life.

The full connection of education with life requires coherence between the organizational aspects and methods of teaching. It is necessary not to introduce various artificial methods and methods into the practice of the educational system, but to achieve their connection with life and existing natural laws. Let the student apply the knowledge he has learned in the lesson in life or make a scientific conclusion based on what he has seen in life. Only then, the knowledge given will settle not only in the student's memory, but also in his thinking and psyche, becoming his property. A student who hears one thing in school and sees something else in life loses faith in the truths taught in lessons. The most correct way is education based on real life facts.

In front of these subjects, the main goal of national pedagogy is to form good moral qualities in students. By teaching the student to be affected by the word, feel it and enjoy it, it is possible to educate beautiful qualities and positive qualities in the human personality with the help of artistic words in literature classes. It is understood through literature that the words and deeds of good-natured, healthy spiritual people are worthy of themselves, and the owner of a pure heart is always worthy of encouragement and blessings. These works are carried out directly by studying works of art, analyzing texts;

- *ensuring the student's participation in education and learning*. In order to ensure the spiritual maturity of the reader, in the process of analyzing the work of art, they are encouraged to express their opinion in the discussion about the events, personality, actions, sufferings and joys of the characters reflected in the text, to support or condemn a point of view or activity. This work is carried out with the help of questions presented on the text of the work, with the help of problem situations. While answering the questions, the student refers to the text of the work, searches, listens to his peers, expresses his views, compares them with others, controls, draws conclusions. In the course of this activity, the student works on the formation of his spirituality and self-education.

Literature is a treasure of manners, and by ensuring the student's access to this treasure at his own will, it will be possible to realize self-education while working on the works and expressing reactions in literature classes;

- *to give the student the taste of discovery*. The reader must discover for himself the artistic and life truths that have been instilled in the work of art by its author, advanced by the creators of the textbook. The reader should be given the opportunity to discover the moral qualities of the heroes of the work with the help of questions based on the text. Discovery is always fun, and students should be given the chance to experience that fun. The taste of discovery encourages the reader to delve deeper into the essence of the work and make new discoveries. A person wants to do the work that gives him presence again and again, to deepen it and feel that presence again. Synchronization of literature lessons with such natural qualities characteristic of a person will bring up a healthy spirituality in the student's personality;

- *ensuring pedagogical cooperation*. In literature classes, the teacher should be a partner, not a governor. Knowledge acquisition and education is carried out by the student

himself in cooperation between the teacher and the student. The main tasks of the teacher in the lesson are to read the work expressively and effectively and to ask the tasks given in the textbook about the text of the work...

It is known that every work is the product of one person's creativity. He even created a sample of folklore. In that work, a person pours out his pain, puts his dreams, painful or happy moments of his life in it. To feel the spirit of the creator of the work, to feel his joys and sorrows is important in the purification of spirituality. When working on the text, evaluating the experiences and personality of the heroes of the work allows the reader to learn about a person and form his identity through acquaintance. One of the important aspects of today's literary education is to understand the writer who was able to make the reader share his joys, sorrows, and sufferings, to make him sympathize with his indifference, and to know his personality by studying his writings. Evaluating the heroes of the work forms students' ability to evaluate the people around them based on their actions;

One of the important directions in education is **a creative approach to it**. A creative approach to teaching is becoming a priority in teaching everything from science and technology to philosophy, the arts, the natural sciences and the humanities around the world. The creative thinking of the individual, which is the basis of the creative approach in education, is a higher concept than the ability to give random ideas. It is a real skill based on knowledge and experience that allows a person to achieve better results in difficult situations. Creative thinking ranks among independent and logical thinking skills in educational practice. Societies and organizations all over the world increasingly feel the need for innovative knowledge and creativity in solving problems, especially in the education system, and this, in turn, further strengthens the direction of innovation and creativity in this field.

The concepts of "creative" and "creativity" (*"create" when translated from Latin and English, "creative" means creator*) describe the ability of an individual to create new ideas and are considered to be **a creative ability that is part of talent as an independent factor**.

First of all, the pedagogue working in the educational system should have the qualities of creativity. This creates the basis for the qualitative and effective organization of his personal abilities and professional activities. Organization of didactic support of teaching based on a creative approach guarantees the effectiveness of the teaching process.

Teacher's creativity in the educational process:

- creating creative questions and tasks that increase students' interest in reading;
- be able to create learning problems based on various pictures, images, tables, diagrams, multimedia materials, electronic literature, internet materials, electronic dictionaries, work in small groups, and direct students to solutions if they are interested in them;
- to be able to distinguish creative, independent and logical thinking skills and independent activities characteristic of students;
- such skills of the students are reflected in the types of work, such as the ability to distinguish the level and make appropriate evaluations.

The ability of the teacher to achieve independent, logical and creative (creative) thinking of his students, to encourage creative activity in the educational process and to encourage such activity is the basis for encouraging others in the class to engage in such creative activity.

A creative (creative) approach to education is the basis of significant innovations for the entire society as a basis for directing students to creative thinking. At the same time, it is also

a universal and equalizing phenomenon. That is, any person, to one degree or another, has the ability to think creatively, independently and logically. According to educational experts and psychologists, the thinking process associated with creative activity has a positive effect on the development of a number of other personal skills. That is, metacognitive (thinking about thinking, knowing about knowledge, the ability to understand the mind) ability is the basis for the formation of interpersonal skills, self-awareness and problem-solving skills. In addition, a creative approach to education is important for personal development, academic success, and future professional and life success.

Based on a creative approach to education, it is possible to develop an individual at the level of the requirements of the international research program aimed at evaluating his creative thinking, and to achieve positive changes in educational policy and pedagogy. Today, the PIRLS and PISA studies also provide clear, reliable, and actionable assessment tools that help administrators make evidence-based decisions about student creative thinking and performance. The results achieved in this regard in the developed countries of the world are the cause of debates about the importance and methods of developing this important skill through education in the students of national education.

The main task of a creative approach to education is to enable the student to live a successful life in society, to form and develop the skills and abilities needed today and in the future. Underpinning this approach, creative thinking and creative activity are critical skills that today's youth must possess. These skills help them adapt to a world that is constantly and rapidly changing, requiring individuals with "21st century skills" beyond simple literacy.

Creative thinking and activity, which is the basis of the process of creative approach to education, is globally recognized as the means of "giving new ideas and solutions". A creative approach to education:

- 1) describe knowledge, observe and feel the situation, sympathize with others;
- 2) search for ideas, development and research of new ideas;
- 3) to discover the connection of knowledge, to present one's point of view interdisciplinary;
- 4) unusual or strong ideas "to play" with;
- 5) new the product imagination make, express, produce exit, create;
- 6) solution novelty admit get and new solutions to find like activity types mean holds _

Creative thinking at school and activity of development importance only work market with is not limited. School young people for creative talents discover in reaching important importance occupation is enough

Also in the creative direction of education creative activity of students their education to get events, experiences and behavior new and personally meaningful method interpretation reach through is supported. The student's fantasy and curiosity creative education in the process hand comes, creative thinking like this mutually agreement to the tool becomes. At school student's motivation (internal need). and interest increase for, all of students creative potential and enthusiasm account receiver of education new forms to the road put necessary. This to study not so much not interested to the students too help to give possible and their own his opinion say, the potential to open service to do can.

a creative approach to education another one row skills like creative thinking and activity too known to the goal directed practical approach through is developed. Some to teachers student's creative thinking and creative activities development study in the program

another study sciences in return as it happens feeling can _ In fact , students all in classes creative thinking and to the activity inclined will be

Creative thinking _ _ and activity knowledge to master directed each one lesson during blindly memorization , repetition instead of research and creativity supports approaches through is developed . Teachers creative activity separate to receive , such to capacities suitable conditions create they know and themselves too students like to creativity inclined to be , har how to work creative approach help give to receive they know need _ Teacher education in the process creativity (creative thinking , creative activity) the way to the body coming regarding sure to the imagination have to be , education in the process in students creative ideas birth for certain time and conditions demand to be done understanding , in practice to this reach take necessary _

creative approach to education students each how original in the field and efficient solutions , achievements and the imagination impressive to appearances take coming ideas create , evaluate and them in practice in application efficient participation reach ability to take over directs .

Another approach that developed countries are leading in educational directions is **cognitive** called **the approach** . **The basis of the concept of "cognitive"** is derived from the Latin word " *sognitio* " , which means *to know, to understand* . The English word " cognitive " means "learned", which means that a person develops skills and abilities to master knowledge by working hard and mentally and spiritually. Today, in the practice of national educational science, the concepts that have been used in the Uzbek language for a thousand years have been brought into the practice of national education in the form of English terms (creative, cognitive) . This is a proof of the distance of the employees of the official organizations from the field, lack of knowledge of educational practice, national methodology science. Whether these terms are still considered "novelty" (like scratching the right ear with the left hand) will have to be discussed about their interpretation.

There are a number of terms associated with this term, such as cognitive grammar, cognitive linguistics, cognitive psychology, cognitive education, and cognitive orientation. The term "cognitive" is understood in connection with processes such as knowledge of objective reality (the world), its perception by a person, memory, explanation and processing of information. As a result of independent reading and learning, the student finds the necessary knowledge, absorbs it to the maximum extent, and this is considered a cognitive (knowledge, mastery) approach to education . In the language of experts, the "cognitive approach" can be understood as a cognitive process in speech activity ¹. The cognitive iv process ends with the acquisition of knowledge.

Today's educational process is called "cognitive approach" to the teaching method, it is meant that the student acquires knowledge not only from the textbook or the information given by the teacher, but also through the activity of searching for additional literature, gaining a certain understanding with the help of guiding questions. In this process, the questions and tasks created by the teacher based on the content of the subject, first of all, should be interesting to the student, and at the same time, they should be in a way that

¹ Leontev A. A. Basic psycholinguistics. – S-Pb.: Smysl. - 2 03- p.

ensures the conscious mastering of the subject and directs him to independent research in this regard. It is the basis of cognitive education.

Instead of the teacher trying to store knowledge in the memory of the students using various methods and methods effectively, and the students simply memorizing or memorizing and repeating the given information, under the guidance of the teacher, the knowledge that he learned independently takes place in his psyche, where it remains for a lifetime. .

In the next period, the terms " *cognitive education*" and "*cognitive approach*" are entering the practice of education of all academic subjects in the national education science . Such education or cognitive approach to education, unlike reproductive education, encourages independent learning, teaches ways of learning based on inquiry, recommends methods, directs the student to independent acquisition of knowledge.

The main goal of cognitive education as one of the directions of psychology and pedagogy is to develop intellectual abilities of the individual. It promotes teaching based on a set of educational strategies aimed at increasing the student's ability to adapt to the acquisition of new knowledge.

Therefore, the principles and approaches of education, in particular, the principles of teaching literature, and directing students to creativity in all aspects, encouraging them to learn and acquire knowledge independently, are the guarantee of the development of the nation and the country.

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